

THE ROLE OF YOUNG LEADERS AND SYSTEM PRINCIPLES IN NEW
UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: *An important issue at the heart of the ongoing reforms in the country is the policy of educating young people. An important aspect of this policy is that it allows young professionals to be more active in the field of governance. This article discusses the role of young leaders in the new Uzbekistan and the principles of the system.*

Kalit so'zlar: *strategic, intellectual potential, professional staff, specialists, young leaders, management style;*

INTRODUCTION

We know that in the new Uzbekistan, youth is an important strategic resource of society. Therefore, the realization of creative, intellectual and entrepreneurial potential of young people in our country, the introduction of innovative ideas, projects and technologies, the promotion of innovative activities of talented students, young scientists and entrepreneurs, science, education and the necessary conditions are being created to strengthen the integration of production.

DISCUSSION

As a result of rapid and radical changes in the socio-economic life of our country, the demand for professionals is growing. The share of young executives in government and business administration is growing. This, in turn, requires that young professionals have sufficient theoretical knowledge and practical skills in leadership to lead the team.

Management is a complex profession that requires adequate training not only in economic, social and psychological knowledge, but also in theory. In addition to general, technical, economic, operational, and organizational skills, a leader must be able to articulate his or her image in a practical way in a wide range of situations by understanding all the facts.

If a leader can't set a personal example in an organization, he or she will not gain a reputation in the community. A leader who does not know the art of management cannot ensure the effectiveness of the decisions made. Thus, the role and importance of leadership style in management is very important, and production results and effectiveness are determined by the knowledge and skills of the manager, management process technology, labor discipline and, above all, the style he uses. The manager's management style influences the end result of the enterprise through the production management function. So, all of this is a single mechanism for managing the activities of the organization.

In addition, organizational skills, business acumen, and initiative are important to a leader's role. Every leader who considers himself a leader is able to see farther than others, to solve the financial and economic problems of the enterprise correctly and rationally, to solve urgent production problems quickly, to distinguish psychologically from subordinates. , should be able to distribute work according to their gender, age, mental and physical capabilities. The positive qualities of a leader, such as the ability to manage people, care for people, initiative, perseverance, independence, assertiveness, the ability to consult with subordinates, to keep their word, are important qualities that adorn his personality. It is important for every young leader to aim for these positive qualities.

An authoritarian style of government is one-man rule, in which there is only one person who holds and exercises power. Such leaders are the focus and activity of the management team.

Authoritarian leaders have the following characteristics:

- makes decisions with individual authority;
- The administrator is constantly involved in the work of subordinates;
- solves all big and small problems on his own, without consulting his subordinates, and sometimes through pressure and domination;
- takes full responsibility for the activities of its subordinates, tries to pass all the information through itself;

The democratic style is characterized by the fact that the young leader relies on the members of the group. Democracy reflects the rule of the people in the interest of the people. Such leaders encourage direct communication between team members, listen to their opinions, and consult with them on a regular basis. This approach of a young leader increases the personal initiative and creative activity of employees, creates a friendly atmosphere in the team.

Democratic-style leaders are distinguished by the following characteristics:

- solves problems in a team spirit;

- tries to explain the decisions made and assignments to the executors and gives instructions if necessary;

- accepts and supports the initiatives of subordinates;
- discusses it extensively among the community before making a decision;

The liberal approach is that the manager does not demonstrate his management skills, but rather refrains from doing so and does not interfere in the affairs of the enterprise. Respects subordinates, listens patiently to their opinions, seeks useful ideas from their suggestions and tries to implement them in practice.

Liberal-style leaders are distinguished by the following characteristics:

- treats all subordinates with respect;
- Dislikes self-expression, openness;
- listens patiently to the opinions of employees, seeks benefits from their suggestions;

CONCLUSION

From the above leadership styles, of course, it is expedient for young leaders to organize democratic governance and governance work accordingly. This means that the democratic method is the most effective system of governance, the application of which increases the likelihood of making the right decisions and ensures labor efficiency.

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